

MANAGEMENT 4.0: EVOLUTION AND INNOVATION IN
ORGANIZATIONAL MANAGEMENT IN THE DIGITAL AGE

Narzullayeva G.S.¹, Saidova D.O.²

¹Narzullayeva Gulchehra Salimovna - teacher

²Saidova Dilnoza Odiljon qizi – student

Department of Economy

Bukhara State University

Abstract. *This article talks about the importance of evolution and innovation in management of the organization in the digital era in the context of management 4.0 and the necessary conditions for their organization. Management 4.0 is a concept that combines advanced strategies, innovative methods and the use of modern information and communication technologies for enterprise administration.*

Keywords. *Management, management 4.0, digital world, evolution, innovation, strategy, technology, business, organization.*

The rapid development of digital technologies, global changes in economics and geopolitics, as well as increasingly dynamic and unstable business conditions require new approaches to management from organizations.

The study is aimed at revealing the essence of this concept by analyzing the evolution of management systems and modern challenges, as well as developing effective strategies and tools for successful modern management, ensuring the competitiveness and sustainability of the enterprise in the market. The end of the 19th - beginning of the 20th century corresponds to the era of scientific management, the founder of which is F. Taylor. The main emphasis in

management of this period was on the rational organization of labor and improving productivity through standardization of processes.

Under the influence of the works of G. Fayol and L. Urwick, the concept of administrative management developed. G. Fayol developed the concept of functional management, in which the organization is divided into divisions, each of which specializes in its own area of activity. He emphasized the importance of management goals and principles that must be established at the top level of the administration. Enterprise management focused on planning, organizing, coordinating and controlling activities.

The principles of administrative management became the basis for the development of a hierarchical structure of functional departments in the organization. By the middle of the 20th century, the attention of management scholars shifted to the quality of products and services. The works of J. Juran and F. Crosby made it possible to create the concept of quality management and implement it in organizations. The success of companies began to depend on their ability to improve the properties of their products, satisfying customer needs.

Key problems and disagreements in the practice of enterprises arose in connection with the need to balance between quality and costs. Increased quality control led to bureaucracy and limited employee creativity. The end of the 20th century is the era of strategic management.

During this period, the emphasis is on developing long-term concepts and adapting to changes in the external environment. M. Porter, in his works on competitive strategies and the competitiveness of an organization, emphasizes the importance of creating unique advantages. In this era, the main difficulties were related to finding a balance between stability and flexibility. Organizations were faced with the need to maintain efficiency in current operations while adapting to rapidly changing market demands.

Since the beginning of the 21st century, we can talk about the transition to the era of innovative management, which is characterized by support for innovation and creativity, the development of flexible and adaptive management methods. The key factors contributing to the change in eras of management were: accelerating the pace of technology development, competition based on innovation, increasing the need for constant development, improvement, increasing the adaptability and flexibility of business processes.

In this regard, the concept of management 4.0 is being formed and developed, combining advanced strategies, innovative approaches and the use of modern information and communication technologies. In our opinion, its key components in modern business conditions include digital tools and technologies, big data analysis, an innovative approach, flexibility and adaptability, increasing the role and involvement of employees in management decision-making, communication and networking, cyber protection.

Modern conditions contribute to the development and improvement of the organization's management system, but not everything is so simple.

Management 4.0 and its development are fraught with many difficulties. The primary problem, most pronounced in conditions, is the insufficient level of development of the digital space and technology. Indicators characterizing the current level of development of the digital space and technologies in Uzbekistan, which determine the capabilities and prospects of management 4.0.

If we look at the statistics, it should be noted that the percentage of domestic organizations using digital technologies is relatively low, although there is a positive growth trend. It is also worth noting positive trends. There is an increase in patent applications for inventions in the field of "Information technologies in management." From 2017 to 2023 their number increased from 86 to 278 units, showing the maximum increase compared to other areas. At the end of 2022, the percentage of applications in the field of management was 11.3%. The

problem of the low level of development of the digital environment and technologies is intensifying against the background of sanctions, a ban on the import of technologies, as well as due to the unpreparedness of the population for global changes of a digital and innovative nature, which is due to the insufficient level of development of competencies and skills.

Another obvious problem of innovation management is the lack of funding. This problem has also aggravated due to the geopolitical events of the present time, which have affected the level of investment attractiveness of companies. The budget deficit means that in the near future there will be problems in government financing of a large number of projects.

In addition to limited access to international markets, technologies, a reduction in the influx of investments and financing, and an insufficient level of development of digital competencies and skills, modern challenges faced by the management of an organization include the risks of losing access to certain resources, as well as reputational risks. Potential opportunities, methods and tools (together - approaches) to overcome the challenges under consideration through the development and implementation of the management concept 4.0 at enterprises.

Management 4.0 development provides companies with a wide range of tools that can help them overcome the challenges associated with modern geopolitical and economic conditions and sanctions. One of the breakthrough technologies in recent years has been the creation of artificial intelligence and its implementation in analytical business processes. This allows for an objective assessment of a large number of development scenarios in a shorter time.

In combination with brainstorming and collective thinking methods, it is possible to find the most effective management methods in a particular situation. Large enterprises are quite successfully introducing tools such as the Internet of

Things, which allows for timely maintenance of machinery and equipment, keeping it in good condition, thereby reducing the capital costs of companies.

Automation and robotization of standard processes help to increase productivity and reduce the human factor, which in the long term affects the cost of production.

The use of modern, including cloud, computing technologies makes it possible to store, process, evaluate and analyze a large array of data, which also increases the objectivity of management decision-making.

A process approach to management, based on optimization and improvement of the organization's functionality, modeled on the basis of the value chain, helps to realize the internal reserves of growth and development of the company, simplifying the organizational structure of subordination. And if earlier its implementation was associated with radical changes in the company, now evolutionary methods for its implementation are being actively developed. Process management and decentralization (including partial) of the administration system significantly increase the flexibility and adaptability of both the organization's management and production lines.

Digital platforms and networks help improve communications with the company's partners and consumers of its products, and can significantly increase the geography of sales. Innovations in education are aimed at implementing training programs and on-the-job training courses, as well as faster adaptation to new technologies and changes in the work environment. All these approaches are ultimately aimed at improving the quality of management and improving the financial performance of the company, which is reflected in the amount of equity capital and its investment attractiveness.

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